

EFFECT OF TEMPERATURE AND CLEARANCE ON SHEAR CUTTING BEHAVIORS IN CFRP LAMINATES

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of the present study is to optimize the shear cutting conditions of CFRP laminates. First, specimens of thermosetting (epoxy) and thermoplastic (polyamide 6) CFRP cross-ply laminates 1.2 mm thick were cut by shearing using lower and upper blades. The shear cutting tests were performed at various temperatures ranging from a room temperature (RT) to temperatures higher than the glass transition temperature T_g . The effect of clearance between the upper and lower blades was investigated only for thermosetting CFRP specimens. Next, cross-sectional and internal damages adjacent to the cutting planes were observed using optical microscopy together with soft X-ray analysis to quantitatively measure the size of burrs, removal parts (lost from the workpiece due to cracking) and delamination area. Finally, double cantilever beam (DCB) and end-notched flexural (ENF) tests were performed to measure the modes I and II interlaminar fracture toughness of the thermosetting CFRP at various temperatures. It was proved from the experiment that the best machining quality, namely, the least delamination area, length of burrs and removal parts, was obtained at a temperature of 70 °C and 45 °C for the thermosetting and thermoplastic CFRP laminates, respectively. These optimum temperatures are lower than T_g , where the interlaminar fracture toughness becomes higher than that at RT while the rigidity is lower than that at RT. The optimum clearance was found to be around 0.05 mm for the thermosetting CFRP laminate. In addition, the maximum shear stress becomes almost constant when the clearance exceeds the optimum one.

1 INTRODUCTION

Carbon fiber reinforced plastic (CFRP) laminates have been extensively employed to various light-weight structures such as aircraft. Recently, CFRP laminates have also been applied to automotive parts. In such an application, mass production is strongly required for reducing manufacturing cost. A press molding process is one of the high-cycle fabrication methods. In press moulding of CFRP laminates made of prepregs, the edge (scrap) portion should be removed from the workpiece for trimming after fabrication. Several machining methods, e.g. drilling and abrasive water jet (AWJ) processes [1-3], have been employed or considered as machining methods for CFRP laminates. However, these methods have disadvantages such as a short-life and high-cost machining tools as well as machining damage including delamination. In addition, an AWJ process requires introduction of a new expensive machining facility. As far as the authors know, shear cutting technique for CFRP laminates has hardly been studied in literature so far. Therefore, we have investigated experimentally and numerically the feasibility of shear cutting of CFRP laminates as a less expensive and high-speed machining method [4-6]. In our previous study, the optimum upper blade geometry was determined and the optimum temperature was found to be a little lower than T_g for the thermosetting CFRP. However, the optimum temperature was not determined for the thermoplastic CFRP. In addition, the effect of clearance between the upper and lower blade has not been clarified yet.

The purpose of the present study is to optimize the shear cutting conditions of thermosetting and thermoplastic CFRP laminates. First, both CFRP specimens (1.2 mm thick) were cut by shearing using lower and upper blades. The shear cutting tests were performed at various temperatures ranging from a room temperature to temperatures higher than the glass transition temperature T_g . The effect of clearance between upper and lower blades was investigated only for thermosetting CFRP specimens. Next, cross-sectional and internal damages adjacent to the cutting portion were observed using optical microscopy together with soft X-ray analysis to quantitatively measure the size of burrs, removal part (lost from the workpiece due to cracking) and delamination area. Finally, double cantilever beam (DCB) and end-notched flexural (ENF) tests were performed to measure modes I and II interlaminar fracture toughness of the thermosetting CFRP at various temperatures.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Shear cutting test

Shear cutting tests were performed for thermosetting CFRP (carbon/epoxy, T700S/#2592, $V_f = 0.6$) and thermoplastic CFRP (carbon/PA6, TENCATE, $V_f = 0.5$) laminates. The stacking sequence for both CFRP laminates is $[0^\circ/90^\circ]_{2S}$ cross-ply lamination with 8 plies. The curing temperature and T_g of the thermosetting CFRP are 130 °C and 89 °C, respectively, while the melting point and T_g of the thermoplastic CFRP are 220 °C and 69 °C, respectively. Here, the T_g of both laminates after their fabrication was measured by using differential scanning calorimetry (DSC). In terms of the thermoplastic CFRP, the stacked prepregs in a mould were preheated in an oven up to 260 °C before cold pressing. The pressure during fabrication was 0.5 MPa and 1.7 MPa for the thermosetting and thermoplastic CFRP, respectively. The both fabricated laminates are 1.2 mm thick and cut into specimens 40 mm long and 10 mm wide.

Figure 1 depicts a schematic diagram showing definition of a clearance angle φ and a shearing angle θ of an upper blade. We used the upper blade with the shearing angle θ of 25°. The clearance angle φ is some positive value, which is a proprietary knowhow of the private company that designed this blade. On the other hand, the clearance angle and the shearing angle of the lower blade are both zero degree. The length of a scrap portion was 10 mm and the rest of the specimen was fixed between the upper plate and the lower blade by two springs at a pressure of 4 MPa. The clearance was changed from 0.01 to 0.1 mm for the thermosetting CFRP whilst the clearance was fixed at 0.05 mm for the thermoplastic CFRP. Shear cutting speed v was chosen to be 1 mm/min since it was confirmed that the effect of cutting speed on machining quality is negligible in the range of v of 1 to 300 mm/min. The specimen was heated up to the predetermined temperatures 25 to 110 °C for the thermosetting CFRP and 25 to 70 °C for the thermoplastic CFRP, respectively, by using a heater inserted near the lower blade. The detail of the experimental setup for the shear cutting tests is described in the literature [6].

2.2 Observation of machining damages

After the cutting tests, the internal damage area including the delamination and the uneven portion

Figure 1: Schematic diagram of shear cutting using an upper blade.

near the cut surface of the specimen was measured by soft X-ray analysis. After this measurement, the specimen was cut in the plane, which is normal to the shear cutting plane and passes through the center of the cutting line. The above cut specimens were then polished for further microscopic observation of the through-the-thickness damage state such as length of burrs and removal parts.

2.3 DCB and ENF tests

The modes I and II interlaminar fracture toughness was measured for the thermosetting CFRP from DCB and ENF tests. The DCB test specimens with the stacking sequence of $[0^{\circ}_{24}]$ are 160 mm long, 26 mm wide and 3.3 mm thick. A polyimide film 25 μm thick (Kapton, DuPont) was inserted in the mid-layer along 37 mm length from the edge of the specimen. The tests were conducted at 25 to 90 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. The ENF test specimens are 110 mm long and the other dimensions are exactly the same as those of the DCB test specimens. The ENF tests were also performed at 25 to 90 $^{\circ}\text{C}$

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Hereafter, the results are the values averaged from five specimens for each condition. Figure 2 demonstrates the average shear strength of the thermosetting and thermoplastic CFRP laminates at various temperatures. Here, the average shear strength is defined as the maximum shear force divided by the cross-sectional area during a cutting process. The average shear strength decreases with increasing temperature. Especially in the thermosetting CFRP, the average shear strength rapidly decreases at temperatures higher than T_g (89 $^{\circ}\text{C}$). This is presumably because the out-of-shear strength decreases due to softening of epoxy resin at elevated temperatures. In contrast, the average shear strength in the thermoplastic CFRP once drops at 45 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and it decreases again at around T_g (69 $^{\circ}\text{C}$). The reason for the first drop is discussed later.

Figure 3 shows optical micrographs of polished cross-sections of the thermosetting CFRP after shear cutting tests at various temperatures. The red lines denote ideal cutting planes while the blue lines denote delamination. The delamination tends to occur at the upper interface of the second and third longitudinal layers from the top. The machining quality becomes the best at 70 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ because the unevenness area is the smallest, resulting in the relatively flat cutting surface. At higher temperatures, thermal shear drops are generated in several layers and the bottom longitudinal layer remains as a burr denoted by the black arrow in Fig. 3 (c).

Figure 4 compares radiographs near the cutting planes of the thermosetting CFRP at temperatures of 25, 70 and 110 $^{\circ}\text{C}$. Delamination area is identified as black or grey zones in these photographs. It is

Figure 2: Effect of temperature on average shear strength in the thermosetting and thermoplastic CFRP.

Figure 3: Cross-sectional views of the planes normal to the cutting planes at 25, 70 and 110 °C in the thermosetting CFRP.

Figure 4: Radiographs near cutting planes at 25, 70 and 110 °C in the thermosetting CFRP.

evident that delamination area is the smallest at 70 °C among the three temperatures.

Figure 5 summarizes the maximum and average length of burrs and removal part as well as delamination area on the cross-sections of the thermosetting CFRP at various temperatures. It can be said that the effect of temperature on the length of burrs and removal part is relatively small. However, temperature dependence of delamination area is clear; namely, it becomes the minimum at 70 °C and increases at temperatures greater than 70 °C.

Figure 5: Maximum and average burrs and removal part length and delamination area on the cross-sections normal to the cutting planes at various temperatures in the thermosetting CFRP.

Figure 6: Effect of temperature on normalized average shear strength, elastic modulus and modes I and II interlaminar fracture toughness of the thermosetting CFRP.

Figure 6 plots the shear strength, elastic modulus, and modes I and II interlaminar fracture toughness G_{IC} and G_{IIC} of the thermosetting CFRP against temperature. The average shear strength and elastic modulus are normalized by the values at 25 °C. The average shear strength and elastic modulus decrease with increasing temperature while G_{IC} increases with an increase in temperature. However, G_{IIC} starts to increase at 90 °C. Combination of the result of Figs. 5 and 6 leads to the conclusion that delamination is constrained the most at 70 °C because moderate softening and improvement of G_{IC} are simultaneously realized at this temperature. Contribution of G_{IIC} to constraining delamination appears only when temperature is higher than 70 °C. However, at temperatures above 70 °C, the effect of softening overcomes the improvement of G_{IC} and G_{IIC} and large thermal shear drops of longitudinal layers cause large delamination.

Figure 7 depicts the typical cross-sectional views normal to the cutting planes of the thermoplastic CFRP cut at temperatures of 25, 40, 45, 50 and 70 °C. The red lines denote ideal cutting planes. Here, the left- and right-side portions of the ideal cutting plane are defined as *burr* and *removal part*, respectively. Unlike the thermosetting CFRP, no delamination is observed at any temperature. Instead,

(a) $T = 25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

(b) $T = 40\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

(c) $T = 45\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$

Figure: 7 (to be continued).

Figure 7: Cross-sectional views of the planes normal to the cutting planes at 25, 40, 45, 50 and 70 °C in the thermoplastic CFRP.

Figure 8: Maximum and average burrs and removal part length and unevenness area on the cross-sections normal to the cutting planes at various temperatures in the thermoplastic CFRP.

the unevenness area due to burrs and removal parts is observed. At the temperatures lower than 45 °C, the burrs are generated in the upper layers while the removal part in the bottom two layers is prominent. In contrast, at the temperatures higher than 45 °C, burrs caused by thermal drops are generated in the bottom layer. At 45 °C, the cutting surface is relatively even although the removal part is observed in the bottom two layers. Figure 8 summarizes the maximum and average length of burrs and removal part as well as the unevenness area on the cross-sections normal to the cutting planes at various temperatures. It is clear that the length of burrs and removal part and the unevenness area become the minimum at 45 °C. Consequently, the cutting shear stress is the minimum and the optimum cutting temperature is concluded to be 45 °C. The modes I and II interlaminar fracture toughness should be measured for more detail discussion in the near future.

Figure 9 plots the average shear strength against clearance at 70 °C which is the optimum cutting

Figure 9: Effect of clearance on average shear strength in the thermosetting CFRP at 70 °C.

Figure 10: Maximum and average burrs and removal part length and delamination area on the cross-sections normal to the cutting planes for various clearances in the thermosetting CFRP at 70 °C.

temperature in the thermosetting CFRP. The average shear strength decreases with increasing clearance for the clearance smaller than and equal to 0.04 mm. This is because the bending stress (normal to the cutting plane) reduces the cutting force for the clearance smaller than the critical value (0.04 mm). However, the average shear strength is kept approximately constant at clearances equal to or greater than 0.04 mm. It is found from the in-situ observation of the cutting process that the shear force reaches the maximum when the upper blade cuts the third layer, namely, the second longitudinal layer from the top. After the shear force reaches the maximum, it rapidly drops and final cutting occurs. For the relatively large clearance, shear deformation becomes dominant whilst the bending stress is small at this final cutting stage. That is why the effect of clearance is negligible for the clearance

Figure 11: Cross-sectional views of the planes normal to the cutting planes at 70 °C and various clearance values in the thermosetting CFRP.

greater than some critical value.

Figure 10 demonstrates the maximum and average burrs and removal part length together with delamination area on the cross-sections normal to the cutting planes for various clearances in the thermosetting CFRP. The maximum and average burr lengths become the minimum at 0.05 mm while the effect of clearance on removal part length is unclear. In addition, the delamination area is independent of clearance in the range of 0.01 to 0.07 mm. However the delamination area tends to increase for the clearance greater than 0.08 mm. Figure 11 depicts the cross-sectional views of the planes normal to the cutting planes at various clearance values in the thermosetting CFRP. The red lines represent the ideal cutting planes. Large shear drops (permanent bending deformation) of the longitudinal layers during cutting is observed when the clearance is greater. This drops cause delamination between the lower longitudinal layer and the upper transverse layer (see blue arrows in Fig. 11 (c)). It is concluded from the result of Figs 9, 10 and 11 that the optimum clearance is 0.05 or 0.06 mm for this CFRP with the thickness of 1.2 mm.

4 CONCLUSIONS

The paper presents the optimum shear cutting conditions of thin thermosetting and thermoplastic CFRP laminates. It was proved from the experiment that the best machining quality was obtained at a temperature of 70 °C and 45 °C for the thermosetting and thermoplastic CFRP, respectively, and that the optimum clearance was 0.05 mm for the thermosetting CFRP. The optimum temperature is strongly correlated with interlaminar fracture toughness, rigidity and shear force required for cutting. The lower limit value of the average shear strength exists even though the clearance is increased since shear deformation mode becomes dominant for larger clearance. Delamination is generated due to shear drop deformation of longitudinal layers, which is remarkably observed at higher temperatures and larger clearances.

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